

REVIEW ON HYDATIDIFORM MOLE**Bhagyashree S., Bhagyashree, Sumithra Devadiga, Savitha Amin and Adarsh V.V.**Department of Pharmacy Practice, Karavali College of Pharmacy, Mangalore, Karnataka,
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Practice, Karavali College of
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A Hydatidiform mole is an abnormal pregnancy in which there are two copies of paternal genetic material. HM's are classified histologically into two types: Complete Hydatidiform moles (CHM) and Partial Hydatidiform moles (PHM), each with its own set of genetic and histopathological alterations. Etiology include parental age, ABO blood groups, history of Gestational trophoblastic disease, Reproductive factors, Oral contraceptive use and other environmental factors. It leads to excessive trophoblastic proliferation and formation of hydropic changes in villous tissue. Clinical signs, symptoms and human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) levels can be helpful in

diagnostic process. The initial treatment of HM in women who wish to preserve fertility is D and C

KEYWORDS: Pregnancy, Trophoblast, Molar pregnancy, Diploid.**INTRODUCTION**

A Hydatidiform mole is an abnormal pregnancy in which there are two copies of paternal genetic material.^[1] In humans, the zygote develops into a blastocyst 5-6 days after conception. The blastocyst's peripheral cells divide into two layers: a cellular trophoblast called the cytotrophoblast (CTB) and an expanding peripheral syncytial layer called the syncytiotrophoblast (STB), which invades the endometrium and uterine vasculature. These two tissues associated with the extra-embryonic mesoderm are at the origin of the placenta. When the proliferation or invasion phenomenon is not well controlled, the trophoblast cells can cause a rare pregnancy complication known as Hydatidiform mole.^[2] It is unique since the tumor originates from gestational tissue rather than the maternal tissue. The most

common type is complete mole, which contains no foetal parts, whereas partial mole may contain detectable foetal residue.^[3]

HM's are classified histologically into two types: Complete Hydatidiform moles (CHM) and Partial Hydatidiform moles (PHM), each with its own set of genetic and histopathological alterations C.^[4] HM's are diploid (2n) with no and thus only contain paternal genetic material (Androgenetic diploidy), and they lack an embryo. PHM's on the other hand are triploid (3n) and biparental. The two paternal copies present in PHM and the triploid embryo, which is incompatible life, distinguish molar from nonmolar triploid pregnancies.^[4]

Epidemiology

The incidence of HM is approximately one in every 1000 pregnancies, though this figure varies greatly across the literature.^[1] This variation could be attributed to underreporting of cases and disparities in data collection and interpretation methods. Recent reports have indicated a decrease in HM trade over time,^[5] which has been linked to dietary changes and improved medical monitoring. On the other hand, have seen an increase.^[1]

Etiology and Risk factors

Etiology include parental age, ABO blood groups, history of Gestational trophoblastic disease, Reproductive factors, Oral contraceptive use and other environmental factors.

Maternal age and a history of Gestational trophoblastic disease have been established as a strong risk factor for Hydatidiform mole.^[6] Other risk factors include genetic basis, spontaneous miscarriage and nutrient restriction, ethnicity.^[7] Molar gestation is more likely in oocytes from older women and teenagers.^[8]

Pathophysiology

Mutations in the NRLP7 and KHDC3L genes, which are associated with maternal imprinting defects, have been implicated in these rare cases of hydatidiform mole.^[8] It is a human pregnancy characterized by excessive trophoblastic proliferation and abnormal embryonic development and it can be sporadic or recurrent. Recurrent hydatidiform mole is defined by the presence of two or more molar pregnancies in the same patient.^[9]

CHM and PHM are genetically different and in that CHM has a normal, diploid number of chromosomes, while PHM is triploid.^[10]

Most CHM are the result of a haploid sperm fertilising of an apparently empty ovum (null nuclear genome) which then duplicates its own chromosome, restoring the diploid chromosome number (homozygous monosporic mole). The chromosome constitution of these moles is usually 46,XX. It is unclear how an unnucleated oocyte is formed, however one possible error could be non disjunction of all chromosomes during meiosis, with all chromosomes ending up in one of the polar bodies.^[10]

PHM's are generally caused by fertilization of an apparently normal haploid ovum by two spermatozoa, though occasional PHM's are caused by the fertilization of an ovum by a diploid sperm. Thus PHM's are triploid in origin with one set of maternal haploid chromosomes and two sets of paternal haploid chromosomes.^[11]

In summary most CHM's have two paternal genome contributions, whereas PHM have both maternal and paternal genome contributions.^[8]

Clinical manifestations

Vaginal bleeding remains the most common presenting symptom and it can occasionally be associated with the passage of hydropic villi. Patients may be anaemic at presentation due to prolonged and occult bleeding. Vaginal bleeding, uterine enlargement greater than expected for gestational age, theca- lutein cysts caused by ovarian hyperstimulation by high serum hCG levels, hyperemesis, preeclampsia, hyperthyroidism and respiratory insufficiency were the classic clinical signs.^[12] Because of the widespread use of ultrasound scans in early pregnancy, many patients are asymptomatic at the time of diagnosis.^[13]

CHM- Karyotype of 46XX, 46XY, diffuse villous enlargement with hydropic changes, varying atypia of trophoblast, absence of fetal tissue and villous capillaries, uterine changes, high hCG levels for gestational age, hypertension and hyperemesis gravidarum, abnormal bleeding, ovarian theca lutein cysts.^[7]

PHM- Karyotype of 69XXX, 69XXY or 69XXYY, placental villi are focal edema and denatured that vary in size and shape, trophoblastic cells proliferate, fetal tissue is present, few full term babies are born, uterus is small for gestational age, few medical complications.^[7]

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of HM is usually suspected on ultrasound imaging. Clinical signs, symptoms and human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) levels can be helpful in diagnostic process.^[14] Diagnosis should always be confirmed by histology with or without ancillary techniques such as genotyping and p57 staining.^[15] It can be improved by including molecular genotyping using either polymorphic STR analysis, or alternatively analysis by whole genome SNP microarray.^[16] In contrast, partial moles and nonmolar gestations have maternal genome and do express the p57 gene. Therefore p57 immunohistochemical staining cannot differentiate partial moles from hydropic spontaneous abortions, but can be helpful in distinguishing complete from partial moles.^[17]

Treatment

Management of Clinically Diagnosed Hydatidiform Mole

I. Pre-evacuation evaluation

- a. Serum quantitative β -hCG
- b. Complete blood count, clotting studies (PT and PTT), renal and liver functions, blood type and screen
- c. Pelvic ultrasound examination
- d. Chest X-ray
- e. Thyroid function tests if hyperthyroidism is suspected

II. Evacuation

- a. Suction D&E
 - i. Serial dilation of cervix without sounding the uterus
 - ii. Begin Pitocin 20 units/L infusion after cervical dilation
 - iii. 12–14 mm suction cannula—initially allow the uterus to involute around the cannula
 - iv. Complete evacuation with suction curettage
 - v. Role of sharp curettage unclear
- b. Hysterectomy should be considered in women older than age 40 y

III. Management after evacuation

- a. Rhogam if Rh-negative
- b. Serial SaO₂ monitoring in patients with uterine enlargement greater than 14 weeks in size
- c. Postevacuation hCG

hCG, human chorionic gonadotropin; PT, prothrombin time; PTT, partial thromboplastin time; D&E, dilation and evacuation; SaO₂, oxygen saturation.^[17] The initial treatment of HM in women who wish to preserve fertility is D and C.^[18] Where available, D and C is performed under ultrasound guidance which helps to remove all molar tissue and avoid uterine perforation. Usually, it is performed under general anaesthesia. 7 Intravenous oxytocin infusion may be started at the onset of suction D&C and may be continued for several hours after operation. The risk of bleeding after suction D&C increases with uterine size. When the uterus is greater than 16 weeks in gestational size, blood transfusion should be available.^[18] Hysterectomy with salpingectomy is an alternative method to suction D&C if molar pregnancy is presumed and childbearing is complete.^[19] Hysterectomy is especially used in women older than 40 years, because these patients have a higher risk of post molar GTN.^[12]

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